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Research Article

**FLUORIDE RELEASE FROM DENTAL ADHESIVE
REINFORCED WITH CALCIUM FLUORIDE OR
FLUORAPATITE**Dr. Amna Urooj¹, Dr. Rauha Sheikh², Dr. Wajeeha Aimen²^{1,2} Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan³ De'Montmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: This study was done to compare the fluoride release from dental adhesive systems (total etch Tetric N-bond and self-etch Tetric N-bond) with the addition of fluorapatite or calcium fluoride in percentages that didn't affect its original shear bond strength for 89 days in vitro.

Place and Duration: In the Dental department of Nishtar Hospital Multan for three months duration from January 2020 to March 2020.

Materials and methods: From each material, 10 cylindrical disk-shaped specimens (diameter: 8.0 mm, height: 1.0 mm) were prepared and immersed individually in 10 ml of deionized water in plastic containers. After 1, 2, 4, 7, 14, 21 and 28 days and after 1 month and 2 months from the last measurement the samples were transferred into new plastic containers that contained 10 ml of deionized water to measure the amount of fluoride in it. The fluoride content was determined with Fluoride Ion Selective Meter HI 96729.

Results: The mean fluoride ion release from each material over the tested periods was recorded and the data were statistically analyzed with ANOVA and LSD tests. Self-etch Tetric N-bond with 7% of its weight of calcium fluoride addition showed the greatest fluoride release over the tested periods among the tested material.

Conclusion: All the tested materials with the addition of fluorapatite or calcium fluoride showed highest fluoride release during the first two days.

Keywords: Fluoride Release, Tooth glue, Fluorapatite, Calcium fluoride, Ion-selective meter HI 96729

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INTRODUCTION:

Dental fillers with various marginal defects are widely used. In clinical trials, secondary gaps were responsible for 72% and 43% of the total number of substitutions required for amalgam and compound restorations. The regenerative material's ability to withstand secondary space attack and micro passes determines whether the restoration has failed¹⁻². Therefore, the addition of an inhibitor to regenerating materials against secondary defects is important due to the difficulty in obtaining an excellent seal on the margins of the cervix. In recent years, the resin compound has been prepared for the release of fluoride. Gradually, a small amount of recurs free from composite recantation will be more useful than a high concentration of periodic fluoride applications. Some studies have found that the inhibition of secondary cavity formation may be influenced by sticky fluoride-containing systems, as fluoride ions released into the hybrid layer penetrate into the dentine³⁻⁴. Dijkman, et al., said that fluor released together per month is enough to inhibit the demineralization of enamel 200-300 g/cm². Long and short-term fluorine regenerating materials are directly related to the fluoride structure, which is contained in the flora content, fluorine regulation mechanism and resin-based materials, and depends on certain environmental conditions. Studies have shown that even if an insufficient amount of fluoride is secreted from tooth glues, crevices can be prevented in the dent⁵⁻⁶. The acid resistance of the cavity margins can be increased in the presence of fluoride and therefore play a role in the cavity walls integrity.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This study was held in the Dental department of Nishtar Hospital Multan for three months duration from January 2020 to March 2020. Initial release studies were performed to select the best ratio of fluorapatite or calcium fluoride additive to the Tetric® N-Bond and Tetric® N-Bond self-etching adhesive, which contained 3% fluorapatite and 5% calcium fluoride for Tetric® N-Bond Bond, while

the best the additive for the Tetric® N-Bond self-etching adhesive was 1% fluorapatite and 7% calcium fluoride. Custom-made silicone molds with an inside diameter of 8 mm and a depth of 1.0 mm were used to prepare disc-shaped cylindrical samples (10 samples of each of the 6 materials tested, which were TE, TE + FA 3%, TE + CaF₂ 5% , SE, SE + FA 1% and SE + CaF₂ 7%). One end of a 10 cm piece of unsafe suture was inserted into each disc sample space by inserting it through a silk thread needle before the material was poured. The adhesive solution was placed in a silicone mold with a slide to cover the top surface, and then light-cured for 40 seconds from the top using a visible light curing device (SDI, Japan) [10]. Each sample was removed from the mold and further light cured for 20 seconds from the bottom. Each sample was immersed and stored in individual plastic containers with 10 ml of deionized water at room temperature. During the fluorine measurement, each sample was removed from the container and the storage solution was decanted for analysis. The sample was returned to a new container with fresh 10 ml of deionized water and storage continued. Each time the solution was changed, the disc was rinsed with fresh deionized water. Fluoride release was measured using a Fluoride Ion Selective Meter at 1, 2, 4, 7, 14, 21 and 28 days and 1 and 2 months after the last measurement. Fluoride release was measured using a Fluoride Ion Selective Meter HI 96729. A mixture of 10 ml of storage solution and 2 ml of fluoride reagent HI 93729-0 was used and the fluoride concentrations were measured in ppm. The results were calculated as the amount of released fluorine per unit area of the sample ($\mu\text{g} / \text{cm}^2$). [11]. The detailed final results are the fluoride release rate ($\mu\text{g} / \text{cm}^2 / \text{day}$) and the cumulative fluoride release ($\mu\text{g} / \text{cm}^2$) which takes into account the area and solution volume of each sample.

RESULTS:

The mean fluoride ion released from each material over the tested periods is represented in Table 1.

Table 1 Mean fluoride ion released ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) from tested materials for the tested periods

Tested Period	TE	TE+FA 3%	TE+CaF ₂ 5%	SE	SE+FA 1%	SE+CaF ₂ 7%
After 1 st day	0	11.104	5.336	0	12.408	12.800
After 2 nd day	0	12.000	4.720	0	11.416	15.328
After 4 th day	0	6.960	3.120	0	6.800	15.152
After 7 th day	0	6.480	5.360	0	4.320	15.880
After 14 th day	0	7.920	9.200	0	5.200	16.000
After 21 st day	0	6.080	7.600	0	1.632	14.944
After 28 th day	0	5.520	7.440	0	2.000	15.568
After 58 th day	0	4.720	13.120	0	2.640	15.968
After 88 th day	0	3.920	12.000	0	2.800	16.000

The mean fluoride ion released from each material over the tested periods for total etch groups shows that the maximum fluoride released from TE+FA 3% were in the first two days, then decreased for the remaining period unless for the 14th day when it increased slightly, while for the TE+CaF₂ 5% the peak level of fluoride ion released was in the 58th day. For the self-etch groups, the mean fluoride ion released from each material over the tested periods shows that the maximum fluoride release from SE+FA 1% were in the first two days then decreased nearly in descending order till the 21st day, the curve became nearly steady for the remaining periods, while the SE+CaF₂ 7% presented higher fluoride ion release for all tested periods.

Table 2 ANOVA test of fluoride ion release means between total etch groups for all tested periods

Tested Period	ANOVA F-test	p-value	Sig
After 1 st day	404.300	<0.001	HS
After 2 nd day	337.900	<0.001	HS
After 4 th day	50.052	<0.001	HS
After 7 th day	61.830	<0.001	HS
After 14 th day	149.200	<0.001	HS
After 21 st day	385.400	<0.001	HS
After 28 th day	149.100	<0.001	HS
After 58 th day	359.500	<0.001	HS
After 88 th day	931.500	<0.001	HS

Analyzing the data using ANOVA test showed a highly significant difference (p less than 0.001) in fluoride release between self-etch groups for all tested periods as shown in Table 3. The amounts of fluoride release from materials were statistically analyzed using the LSD test for comparison among the materials. For total etch groups at 7th day there was non-significant difference between TE+FA 3% and TE+CaF₂ 5% at (p less than 0.05) and at the 14th day there was a significant difference between them at (p less than 0.01) for all the tested periods between materials unless in the first tested day there was a non-significant difference at t (p 0.05) between SE+FA 1% and SE+CaF₂ 7%.

Table 3 ANOVA test of fluoride ion release means between self-etch groups for all tested periods

Tested Period	ANOVA F-test	p-value	Sig
After 1 st day	365.40	<0.001	HS
After 2 nd day	612.80	<0.001	HS
After 4 th day	149.50	<0.001	HS
After 7 th day	281.90	<0.001	HS
After 14 th day	175.60	<0.001	HS
After 21 st day	398.10	<0.001	HS
After 28 th day	651.80	<0.001	HS
After 58 th day	107.90	<0.001	HS
After 88 th day	115.07	<0.001	HS

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

One method of measuring fluorine reacts with a red fluoride sample reagent, and the interaction between fluoride and the reagent leads to a reduction in the red color of the reagent, and as the fluoride concentration increases, the color of the reagent becomes brighter than that detected by the silicon photodetector. Each time the device is used for measurement, it has a locking system that helps to place the bucket in the same position⁹⁻¹⁰. In addition, it has an indicator for the cooling lamp to allow the sample element to cool down before each measurement for greater readability. The deficiency of this product indicates that it may determine the fluoride concentration between 0,0-2 mg/l (PPM) and its inability to determine the amount of fluoride greater than 2 mg/l exceeds only 2 mg/l. Unlike fluoride, GIC or RMGI, it is placed on resin, which limits the release of fluoride, which leads to thinking about fluorine-free adhesive systems, and this study helps to strengthen the adhesive system with fluoride or calcium fluoride¹¹⁻¹². All fluoride adhesives showed a continuous release of fluoride water into deionized water during the test periods (88 days). According to the following equation, the oscillation of fluorine does not depend on the weight, but on the exposed surface: mgF/cm^2 to ppm (WR/ml) ml (unit storage volume) 1/surface of each sample material is tested as 1,25 cm². Cylinder surface $2\pi r(r+h)$. During the first two days, each fluoride adhesive showed the release of the most fluoride, and is in harmony with Atsushi, and others, and so on, as the first fluoride eruption released from the surface¹³⁻¹⁴. On day 4, all fluorine groups se + CaF₂ 7% may be due to a decrease in fluoride release, and a high percentage of this fluoride content can lead to high availability of fluoride transmission to the sample surface. Fluoride decreases after two days due to the spread of a small amount of fluoride into the environment for other groups, and in the event that it is dealt with by Itota, et al, Wiegand, et. While fluorine adhesive continues to reduce fluoride release, TE+ CaF₂ increases by 5% at half-time and can be caused by this high fluoride content, and caF₂ is easily released in the presence of fluorine water, 7% SE + CaF₂ releases the most fluoride during the period considered. One of the main reasons for replacing renovations is usually secondary gaps associated with micro-sealants between teeth restoration interfaces. Dijkman, et al., said that the accumulated fluoride released in 200-300 g/cm² months was sufficient to completely inhibit the mineralization of the mine. In this study, the cumulative release of fluoride is released with fluoride adhesive swings accumulated above 200 g/cm² per month with the release of accumulated fluoride, while fluorine adhesives are supplemented with a fluoride-free oscillation of less than 200 g/cm² per month, while TE+FA 3% is secreted in

the first month of more than 200 g/cm²¹⁵. Even a small amount of fluoride will reduce the demineralization of tooth tissue, which is constantly released around the tooth, This means that all fluoride adhesives in this study will help prevent demineralization and improve remineralization, because for all proven periods, fluoride ions are crucial for increasing the strength of the tooth structure, as the transformation of flupatiate hydroxyapatite will be used in addition to its reaction with dissolved calcium and phosphate during an attack. Itota, and others, Wiegand, et al, et moreau, et al., Fluoride released from various fluorovor regenerating materials declares that in pH 4.0 a severe acidity has improved, which means that if, instead of more deionized fluorescent water, this fluoride shows that fluoride will be more free of bacterial acidogenic episodes, which will help prevent demineralization by combining free fluoride with dissolved calcium and phosphorus and hydropathy. The first version of fluoride from FA reinforced adhesive may be due to the initial surface rinsing effect and due to the ability of fluoride to spread to the surface the next day, the release of a high amount of fluoride according to fa glue groups into CAF₂ may be caused by the dissolution of inorganic fluoride by high water sorption from the matrix region, in addition to the high percentage of fillers. Statistically, 7. For automatic etch groups, only a large amount of fluoride release occurred on the first day, which had a slight difference between 7% se + FA% and SE + CaF₂. In all other periods there was a very significant difference between the CaF₂ groups and the FA groups.

REFERENCES:

1. Gholam, Mohammed Kassim, and Mohammed R. Hameed. "Fluoride Release from Dental Adhesive Reinforced with Fluorapatite or Calcium Fluoride." *International Journal of Medical Research & Health Sciences* 7, no. 9 (2018): 137-143.
2. Moshaverinia, Maryam, Ali Borzabadi-Farahani, Abdi Sameni, Alireza Moshaverinia, and Sahar Ansari. "Effects of incorporation of nano-fluorapatite particles on microhardness, fluoride releasing properties, and biocompatibility of a conventional glass ionomer cement (GIC)." *Dental materials journal* 35, no. 5 (2016): 817-821.
3. Dickens, Sabine. "Single solution bonding formulation." U.S. Patent 6,649,669, issued November 18, 2003.
4. Barandehfard, F., M. Kianpour Rad, A. Hosseinnia, K. Khoshroo, M. Tahriri, H. E. Jazayeri, K. Moharamzadeh, and L. Tayebi. "The addition of synthesized hydroxyapatite and fluorapatite nanoparticles to a glass-ionomer cement for dental restoration and its

- effects on mechanical properties." *Ceramics International* 42, no. 15 (2016): 17866-17875.
5. Büyükyılmaz, T., and B. Øgaard. "Caries-preventive effects of fluoride-releasing materials." *Advances in dental research* 9, no. 4 (1995): 377-383.
 6. Melo, Mary AS, Sarah FF Guedes, Hockin HK Xu, and Lidiany KA Rodrigues. "Nanotechnology-based restorative materials for dental caries management." *Trends in biotechnology* 31, no. 8 (2013): 459-467.
 7. Nicholson, John W. "Fluoride-releasing dental restorative materials: An update." *Balkan Journal of Dental Medicine* 18, no. 2 (2014): 60-69.
 8. Dickens, Sabine H., and Glenn M. Flaim. "Effect of a bonding agent on in vitro biochemical activities of remineralizing resin-based calcium phosphate cements." *Dental materials* 24, no. 9 (2008): 1273-1280.
 9. Rodriguez-Lorenzo, L. M., J. N. Hart, and K. A. Gross. "Influence of fluorine in the synthesis of apatites. Synthesis of solid solutions of hydroxy-fluorapatite." *Biomaterials* 24, no. 21 (2003): 3777-3785.
 10. Gul, Hashmat, Saba Zahid, Shahreen Zahid, Muhammad Kaleem, Abdul S. Khan, and Asma T. Shah. "Sol-gel derived fluoride-doped bioactive glass powders: Structural and long-term fluoride release/pH analysis." *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* 498 (2018): 216-222.
 11. Nicholson, John W. "Fluoride-releasing dental restorative materials: An update." *Balkan Journal of Dental Medicine* 18, no. 2 (2014): 60-69.
 12. Rodriguez-Lorenzo, L. M., J. N. Hart, and K. A. Gross. "Influence of fluorine in the synthesis of apatites. Synthesis of solid solutions of hydroxy-fluorapatite." *Biomaterials* 24, no. 21 (2003): 3777-3785.
 13. Xu, Xiaoming, and John O. Burgess. "Compressive strength, fluoride release and recharge of fluoride-releasing materials." *Biomaterials* 24, no. 14 (2003): 2451-2461.
 14. Bayrak, Gokcen Deniz, Nuket Sandalli, Senem Selvi-Kuvvetli, Nursen Topcuoglu, and Guven Kulekci. "Effect of two different polishing systems on fluoride release, surface roughness and bacterial adhesion of newly developed restorative materials." *Journal of Esthetic and Restorative Dentistry* 29, no. 6 (2017): 424-434.
 15. Chen, Wen-Cheng, Chien-Ping Ju, Jen-Chyan Wang, Chun-Cheng Hung, and Jiin-Huey Chern Lin. "Brittle and ductile adjustable cement derived from calcium phosphate cement/polyacrylic acid composites." *Dental Materials* 24, no. 12 (2008): 1616-1622.